

A NEW CUPRAMMONIUM PROCESS FOR THE FINISHING OF CELLULOSIC TEXTILES

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A new cuprammonium process for finishing cellulosic material has been described. The effect of the finishing treatment on the various properties of the treated material has been studied.

Comparative permanence and improvement in handle and appearance are now the main objectives of the finisher, and cotton is regarded as the textile material for which there is the greatest need for such finishing treatments. If the arguments for this separation of cotton as a class, distinct from wool, rayons and silk, are carried further, the short-staple cottons are in greater need of chemical finishes than the soft lustrous long-staple cottons.

India is one of the major cotton growing countries of the world, but the crop consists mainly of short-staple cotton which does not seem to be capable of being used for the manufacture of superior quality fabrics by our mills. It is this inferiority by way of appearance of short-staple cotton fabrics that renders it necessary to study the latest development in chemical finishing. There is little doubt that the feel and appearance of fabrics made in Lancashire from short-staple cottons are concerned with some of the newer methods of chemical finishing. With a view to improving the quality of short-staple cotton textiles and also to increasing the home consumption of short-staple cotton, the present work was undertaken.

In the development of a chemical finish, suitable for the short-staple cotton fabrics, due regard must be given to the ease with which raw materials can be obtained and at the same time encroachment on existing patent literature must be avoided. A survey of the various chemical finishes suggests that the cuprammonium finishing process could be easily adopted for the processing of Indian short-staple cotton fabrics. The chemicals required, viz., copper, ammonia, caustic soda and sulphuric acid, are easily available in this country. Also the existing patent literature does not cover the ground very widely.

The oldest finishing process known to employ cuprammonium hydroxide is the Willesden process for the rot- and water-proofing of sailcloth¹. The various modern cuprammonium processes are only modifications of the above process, and may be classified thus :

(i) *Arnold print works method*².—The fabric is padded through a solution of caustic soda of more or less than mercerizing strength and with or without drying is passed through a solution of a cuprammonium salt. This is followed by souring, washing and drying. The order of treatment with caustic soda and cuprammonium may be reversed³

(ii) *Heberlein and Co.* have patented a process⁴ in which the solution of a cuprammonium salt is activated by addition of an alkali metal hydroxide to the extent of 0.5 to 1.5%. The coagulation may be effected either by dilute acid or by caustic soda of mercerizing strength.

(iii) *Morton Sundour Fabrics*⁵ impregnate the fabric with a solution of copper sulphate and follow it by treatment with caustic soda and ammonia in single or separate baths.

(iv) *Wm. H. Furness*⁶ claims the use of a double salt from 1 mole of copper sulphate, 4 moles of ammonia and 2 moles of caustic soda dissolved in excess of ammonia.

After experimenting with short-staple cotton fabrics, using the already patented methods and studying their effects on the fabrics, a new method has been developed. Processes using ready-made cuprammonium solution suffer from the disadvantage that the solution is sensitive to light, air and temperature. So the solution has to be stored in dark and at a low temperature. In the new process developed in the present investigation, the cuprammonium hydroxide solution is formed *in situ* on the fabric, and once it is formed, it can be kept in contact with the fabric for the desired time depending on the structure of the fabric. The fabric is then squeezed and soured in sulphuric acid solution to reprecipitate the dissolved cellulose and remove copper and ammonia. The fabric is then washed and dried, in open width.

This treatment has been found to produce about 5 to 10% increase in tensile strength, altered surface properties, much cleaner appearance and the feel obtained is more or less permanent after several laundry washes. The treated fabric has been examined for its absorption of colour in dyeing and printing. The dyeing properties are similar to those of linen. The shades obtained by dyeing and printing are brighter on the finished fabrics as compared with those on the unfinished samples. The prints are clear

and sharp due to the removal of projecting loose fibres by dissolution during the finishing treatment. The light, rubbing and washing fastness of the dyed and printed finished samples have been compared with the unfinished sample. Certain samples have been first dyed or printed and then subjected to the finishing treatment and their fastness properties have been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals used.—Commercial caustic soda is available both as flakes and as fused lumps. Latter contain about 60% caustic soda and 40% water. The flakes are 98-99% pure with sodium oxide content of 76%, the main impurity being sodium carbonate. The caustic soda is dissolved in equal weight of water, allowed to cool and filtered through asbestos wool. The clear solution is diluted with water to the required concentration. The strength of the solution is checked by a Twaddlemeter.

Copper sulphate is marketed as blue crystalline lumps having the composition $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is dissolved by stirring the lumps in hot water. The solution is then allowed to cool and filtered. The amount of the copper is estimated iodimetrically.

Ammonia is available as liquor ammonia (d 0.880) containing 350 g. NH_3 per litre. It is stored in pressure bottles, which are cooled in ice before opening for taking out the ammonia solution for dilution. The strength of the liquor ammonia may be obtained fairly accurately by determining its specific gravity and referring to the standard tables. It may also be conveniently determined by titration with $2\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ of an aliquot portion suitably diluted with water, using methyl orange or a drop of copper sulphate solution as an indicator.

Commercial sulphuric acid comes on the market as a colorless to light brown oily liquid of specific gravity 1.84 (168°Tw) and containing 98% of the monohydrate by weight. The acid is diluted by addition in a thin stream to a large bulk of cold water with continuous stirring. The dilution is carried out in glazed porcelain or leadlined vessels.

Various dyes of the azoic, vat and solubilised vat classes have been applied to the treated and untreated material by the standard procedures available for printing and dyeing.

Materials of construction.—Cuprammonium hydroxide has a highly corrosive action on many metals and it dissolves wood. The most suitable materials of construction are vulcanite and hard rubber for the guide rollers and the bowls of the padding mangles. The troughs for the mangles ~~there~~ of porcelain or rubberlined.

Fabrics.—The fabrics with one exception have been received as grey fabrics in the loom state. The materials were subjected to a standard purification treatment, consisting of desizing, kier boiling and bleaching.

Preparation of cuprammonium hydroxide solution.—Several methods are described in literature for the preparation of cuprammonium hydroxide solution: (a) consisting in bubbling air through ammonia in which copper¹⁻⁹ in the form of powder, gauze or turnings is suspended; (b) consists¹⁰ in dissolving freshly precipitated copper hydroxide in strong ammonia. The preparation and utilisation of stock solutions of cuprammonium hydroxide suffer from certain disadvantages, such as long time for preparation, high cost of the process and the unstable character of the solution, necessitating its being stored away from light and air and at a low temperature. To get over these difficulties the method of preparation of cuprammonium has been modified so that the cuprammonium hydroxide is produced on the fabric during processing. The method has been described in detail below.

Production of cuprammonium hydroxide solution on the fabric.—The fabric is padded through a solution of caustic soda of less than mercerizing strength. The caustic solution impregnated fabric is squeezed and padded through copper sulphate solution, when a blue precipitate of cupric hydroxide is formed on the fabric. The fabric containing the precipitate is squeezed and passed through a trough containing a strong ammonia solution, when cuprammonium solution is formed on the fabric. The solution thus formed is allowed to exert its solvent action for the requisite time and then the fabric is squeezed to force the cuprammonium cellulose solution into the fabric, where it is reprecipitated by souring in dilute sulphuric acid when copper and ammonia are removed. The fabric is then washed and dried. The effect of this treatment on the cloth depends on several factors, such as (i) concentration of caustic soda, (ii) concentration of copper, (iii) time of contact of the fabric with the cuprammonium solution, (iv) degree of squeezing and (v) use of wetting agents. A thorough investigation of these factors by varying the conditions of finishing has been made and the optimum conditions have been arrived at.

The earlier experiments were all carried out on 12" wide pieces of cloth. For this purpose an assembly of various units required was made. After the optimum conditions for this small-scale finishing were finalised, the process was tried on full width fabrics in a continuous manner.

Comparison of the various properties of the treated fabric with those of the untreated fabric.—The treated fabric has a cleaner and more lustrous appearance due to the cleaning of the interstices and removal of the loose surface fibres

due to the solvent action of the finishing agent. It has also a linen-like feel and possesses a fuller handle due to the reprecipitation of dissolved cellulose. The treatment results in an increase in tensile strength to the extent of 5 to 10%. The treated fabric is stiffer and the weave becomes more pronounced.

Dyeing and printing properties of the finished material.—During the passage of the cloth through sulphuric acid, the dissolved cellulose is reprecipitated on the surface of the fabric and forms a film. The penetration of the dyes into the fabric therefore becomes a matter of some consequence. From the point of view of penetration, the fabric may be compared to linen. For vat dyeing the pigment-padding method was found to be the most suitable. The dyeings are quite even and under identical conditions of processing the treated fabrics give a better colour yield, thus compensating for a part of the cost of the finishing process. Similar increase in affinity for dyes was observed when the treated and untreated materials were subjected to printing trials. The increase in affinity of the dyes for the treated fabric was more than what could be accounted for by the initial caustic soda treatment alone. Prints are also brighter and have a sharp outline. The dyed and printed samples were subjected to an examination for rubbing fastness, since it was thought that the reprecipitation of the cellulose after cuprammonium treatment might form a film more resistant to penetration during dyeing and printing than the original fabric, thus resulting in a badly rubbing material. The rubbing fastness was tested by the official method of the American Textile Chemists Association¹ and consists in giving twenty backwards and forwards strokes in a Crock-meter on the dyed samples using a moist white calico. The rubbing fastness of the dyeings and prints on treated and untreated fabric do not differ substantially.

Certain fabrics were first dyed and printed with a number of vat colours and then subjected to the finishing treatment. During the finishing treatment no bleeding of colour took place. In most cases the shade became brighter but with some colours, such as Caledon Blue R, a slight dullness in tone resulted. The rubbing fastness of the finished and unfinished pieces were determined on the Crock-meter¹. In almost all cases the rubbing fastness was improved after finishing.

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R E F E R E N C E S

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- *N. B.*—The process described above is covered by Indian Patent No. 37379 of 1948.